

Increasing Interest for the Scandinavian Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Psychology

Ole Jakob Storebø and Sven Bölte

We are now entering the second year of the Scandinavian Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Psychology (SJCAPP). A look at the web-statistics demonstrates a steady increase in the number of visitors to our journal. Figure 1 shows the number of unique SJCAPP site visitors per month since the journals launch in November 2012. Many visitors use the SJCAPP site regularly, so the total number of monthly visitors is significantly higher.

FIGURE 1. No. of unique visitors to the SJCAPP homepage (11/2012-12/2013) [Google Analytics]

Figure 2 shows the geographical distribution of these visitors. The visitors' origins indicate a broad international interest for SJCAPP.

FIGURE 2. Global distribution of SJCAPP visitors

An increasing interest for SJCAPP is also suggested by the rising numbers of submitted papers. For instance, the journal received ten proposals for

our special issue on autism which will be published in March/April this year.

We are happy to be an independent Journal, free from economical, governmental or industrial constraints. Our Journal is based on the willingness from volunteers to work for free and thereby ensure the fundament for the open access. However, a minor publication fee might not be avoidable in the future for reasons of financial sustainability. Another aim of the editor's is to develop the Journal towards a living "entity". For instance, in March 2014 we will arrange an autism symposium with researchers from the journal's editorial board as main speakers. Lectures and a pro con discussion on DSM 5 issues will be recorded as podcasts and published in the Journal. Consistently, in the second year, the Journal's homepage is further improved. Among other things, a new feature will be available making it easy for our readers to comment on articles by using a "Comment button".

Dear readers; please spread the word about the Scandinavian Journal of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Psychology, use it as your choice for publication, and encourage others to do so. With your help, the SJCAPP will reach its full potential.